

Original article

Comparative diagnostic techniques for cryptosporidium infections among persons living with HIV in Maiduguri, northeast Nigeria

Mairo U. Kadaura¹, Askira M. Umoru,² Jibril Abubakar,¹ Abubakar S. Baba,³ Yakubu M. Yakubu,⁴ Kellu B. Ali,³ Batula B. Daggash,⁴ Shettima A. Baba,⁴ Abdulkarim Abdullahi,⁵ Yahaya Mohammed,⁶ Galadima B. Gadzama,³ Sambo B. Zailani.³

Authors Affiliation

¹Department of Medical Microbiology and Parasitology, Faculty of Basic Clinical Sciences, Federal University of Health Sciences, Azare

²Department of Medical Laboratory Sciences, University of Maiduguri

³Department of Medical Microbiology and Parasitology, Faculty of Basic Clinical Sciences, University of Maiduguri.

⁴Department of Medical Microbiology and Parasitology, University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital

⁵Department of Medical Biochemistry, Federal University of Health Sciences, Azare

⁶Department of Medical Microbiology and Parasitology, Usman Danfodiyo University Teaching Hospital.

Corresponding author: Mairo Usman Kadaura, Email: Mairokadaura@fuhsa.edu.ng, Tel +2347067035380

Abstract

Background: Cryptosporidiosis is an AIDS-defining infection with a high morbidity and sometimes a high mortality rate. The conventional diagnosis, such as the Modified Ziehl Neelsen stain (MZN) of cryptosporidium, requires observation of the infective oocysts; however, their tiny size yields indistinct results, thus limiting the effectiveness of the conventional diagnostic technique. Due to the aforementioned limitation, some techniques like enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) and polymerase chain reaction are techniques with better sensitivity and specificity. The study was carried out to assess the efficacy of the diagnostic methods for the detection of cryptosporidiosis among HIV patients with diarrhoea in Maiduguri. **Materials and Methods:** A total of 269 HIV seropositive patients with diarrhoea attending the ARV clinic at the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital were selected consecutively, and stool samples were collected and examined for oocysts and antigen of cryptosporidium using MZN and Enzyme-Linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) methods, and PCR, respectively. Data were analysed using SPSS, while the sensitivity, specificity, and positive and negative predictive values were calculated manually. **Results:** Among the 269 enrolled patients, the prevalence of Cryptosporidiosis is 13.4% using MZN, 17.1% using ELISA, and 19.3% using PCR. Thirty-six (13.4%) were positive by the modified ZN staining method, with a sensitivity of 30.8%, specificity of 90.8%, a Positive predictive value of 44.4%, and a negative predictive value of 84.5%. ELISA had a sensitivity of 80.8% and a specificity of 98.2% using PCR as the gold standard, with a positive predictive value of 91.3% and a negative predictive value of 95.5%. **Conclusion:** Cryptosporidium infection was highly prevalent among HIV seropositive individuals in Maiduguri. We therefore re-emphasised the need for inclusion of Cryptosporidium screening and treatment in people living with HIV.

Keywords: Cryptosporidium, ELISA, HIV, PCR, ZN stain

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Introduction

Cryptosporidium is one of the most prevalent opportunistic protozoan causes of diarrhoea in immunocompromised individuals, and is a major cause of morbidity and mortality among such populations; however, it has been globally neglected.¹ It is estimated that approximately 30% of the adult population in developed countries and about 60% in developing countries have immunological evidence of exposure to such organisms.² Besides causing mortality and morbidity, cryptosporidiosis has been associated with impairment of physical and intellectual development as well as worsening of nutritional status during infancy.³ Despite that, the existing routine diagnostic methods utilised for detecting *Cryptosporidium spp* are the microscopic analysis of stool smears through staining methods such as Ziehl-Nelson.⁴ Several techniques are used for the laboratory detection of *Cryptosporidium spp* in faecal samples. However, they are usually not detected

using direct microscopic examination of specimens in the absence of special stains; on the other hand, monoclonal antibodies (for the immunosorbent-antigen test ELISA) are used in standard assays in clinical laboratories to increase the efficiency of the conventional method.⁵ Compared to antigen detection, the sensitivity of stool examination by acid-fast staining remains poor and requires an oocyst concentration of over 500,000 per mL in formed stools,⁵ with fewer cases being detected by acid-fast staining than by immunosorbent assay. Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays (ELISAs) have been reported to be up to 10 times more sensitive than acid-fast staining,⁴ making the ELISA method currently the “gold standard” for antigen detection in infected stool samples.⁶ With the development of molecular epidemiology, more and more data are available worldwide, enabling a better knowledge of the distribution of *Cryptosporidium spp.*⁵ Globally, Cryptosporidiosis is ranked the 5th parasitic agent of diarrhoea among the 24 most important borne parasites.⁷ Most infections are self-limited, but recurrences are common in endemic areas. Chronic infection can lead to weight loss, and malabsorption is associated with stunting (low height for age), wasting (low weight for height), and cognitive impairment in children in developing countries.⁸ Recent studies have also linked cryptosporidiosis to colorectal cancer. Cryptosporidiosis remains a common cause of chronic diarrhoea in AIDS patients in developing countries, with up to 74% of AIDS patients with diarrhoea harbouring microorganisms in their stool.⁹

This study was conducted because of the increasing documentation of infection by *Cryptosporidium spp* and the fact that it regularly eludes diagnosis in clinical laboratories. An understanding of the best technique will reduce its underdiagnosis and treatment. We hope to compare microscopy (MZN) and ELISA against PCR.

Materials and Methods

Setting

The study was conducted from April 2020 to March 2021 at the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital, Borno State. This was a cross-sectional, prospective study that involved adult people living with HIV who gave consent. Microscopy and immunological analysis were done at the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital Department of Medical Microbiology and Immunology, while the molecular analysis was done at the biotechnology centre University of Maiduguri.

Patient recruitment

Each patient enrolled in this study gave informed consent by either signing or thumb-printing the consent form. The questionnaire consists of a sociodemographic section, past medical history, clinical section, and laboratory section. The questionnaire was administered by the research assistant at the ARV Clinic. All Persons living with HIV who were 18 years and above, regardless of gender, who presented to the antiretroviral (ARV) clinic or were admitted to UMTH on account of diarrhoea and on highly active antiretroviral therapy (HAART) were recruited in the study. People living with HIV with diarrhoea and who are on prophylactic antihelminthics

were excluded from the study.

Sample Collection

Two hundred and sixty-nine (269) stool samples were collected in a universal sterile container and transported to the Department of Medical Microbiology, UMTH. The samples were divided into three portions. The first was frozen, the second part was concentrated and aliquots frozen, and the third was used for MZN.

Microscopic Examination/ Macroscopic Examination

The stool sample was examined macroscopically for consistency and the presence of mucus or blood. A direct wet mount with iodine was done to identify some intestinal parasites present.

Stool Concentration

Approximately 2g of fresh stool was mixed with 10 ml of PBS solution in a clean container using a clean rod. The mixture is filtered through a mesh. The filtrate was collected, and 4ml of ether was added to a tube and shaken to obtain a homogeneous mixture. This tube was centrifuged at 2000rpm for 3min to break the emulsion. At the end of this step, the tube showed three different phases. The top is the ether phase, a lipophilic phase (residue layer), and the pellets. The tube is then emptied abruptly. Using a Pasteur pipette, two drops of the pellet are spread between slides and smeared to be stained using the MZN.

Modified Ziel-Nelson Staining MZN

Concentrated faecal samples were thinly smeared on a glass slide, air dried, fixed with methanol for 5 minutes, and stained by the modified Ziehl-Neelsen technique. The slides were stained with carbolfuchsin for 5 minutes and washed with water. The slide was decolourised with 2.5% acid alcohol for 1 minute and counter-stained with 1% methylene blue for 1 minute, then washed and air dried. Finally, the smears were microscopically examined using a 100X objective.

Antigen detection:

The required number of wells needed was broken with the addition of two wells for the positive and negative control, and two drops of stool supernatant were added to each well, including those of the controls. It was then incubated for 30 minutes at a temperature (15-25°C, then washed. After the last wash, the wells were slapped out on a clean paper towel in order to remove excess buffer. Two drops of anti-*Cryptosporidium* antibody reagent were added to each well and incubated for 5 minutes at room temperature. After washing, 2 drops of chromogen were added and incubated for 5 minutes. It was then washed, and 2 drops of stop solution were added to each of the wells and mixed gently by tapping the side of the holder with the index finger for approximately 15 seconds. The reaction was read within 5 minutes after adding the stop solution.

Molecular Detection

DNA extraction

DNA extraction and PCR were done on the aliquots of the stool sample after defrosting it. First, all the clinical samples were subjected to DNA extraction using commercially available QIAamp stool Minikit (Qiagen, Germany) as per the manufacturer’s instructions, with some modifications as described by Okojoku *et al*¹⁰. Faecal suspensions were prepared by adding saline (0.8%

w/v) in a ratio of 1:1 (v/v). Next, fecal material (0.1 ml) was added to 1.4 ml of alkali wash solution (0.5 M NaOH and 0.05 M sodium citrate) in a 1.5 ml Eppendorf tube and mixed for 30 seconds at room temperature by repeated inversion. The mix was subsequently centrifuged at 13,000g for 5 min, and the cell pellet containing any cryptosporidial DNA was re-suspended in 0.5 ml of 0.5 M Tris-HCl (pH 8.0) and centrifuged at 13,000g for 5 min. This latter step was repeated, and the resulting pellet was re-suspended in Tris-EDTA (0.1 ml, 10 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8.0, containing one mM EDTA) and the DNA extracted from the oocysts by 10-14 cycles of freeze-thawing (in ice for 1 min; in a water bath at 100°C for 1 min). The resulting extract was centrifuged at 13,000g for 15 min, and the supernatant containing cryptosporidia DNA was transferred to a clean tube and stored frozen before PCR. This procedure took place at the University of Maiduguri Biotechnology Center.

Nested PCR amplification and extension. A nested PCR targeting the small subunit of the 18S-rRNA gene was performed at the University of Maiduguri biotechnology center, with the use of Initial primers Cr18PA: (5' -TTC TAG AGC TAA TAC ATG CG-3') and Cr18PB: (5'-CCCAT TCC TTC GAA ACA GGA-3') amplified a 1.3 kb fragment of the 18S-rRNA gene. The inner primer Cr18NA: 5'-GGA AGG GTT GTA TTT ATT AGA TAA AG-3' and Cr18NB: 5'-CTCATA AGG TGC TGA AGG AGT A-3' amplified an 826-864 bp fragment of the former amplified sequence. The reaction mixture of the PCR consists of 3µl, 1X PCR buffer (50mM KCL, 20 mM Tris-HCL, 2.5 mM Mgcl₂, pH8.4) and 1µl, of 0.1 µg/ml BSA, 2µl of the initial primers, and 1µl of 0.3mM concentration of each of dNTPs, 0.5µl of recombinant Taq polymerase and two µl of the purified DNA and 2µl of 1.5 mM Mgcl₂. The reaction mixture was prepared as described above for the second round of amplification, except for the primers and DNA template. Again, one µl of the first PCR product as a source of DNA and the inner primers was used. Primary amplification was carried out in 35 cycles, each consisting of 95°C for 30 seconds, 45°C for 30 seconds, and 68°C for 30 seconds, with an initial denaturation at 95°C for 3 min and a final extension at 68°C for 5 min. Thirty-five cycles were used for secondary amplification, with identical temperatures and times, with an annealing temperature of 48 °C. All PCRs were run in a Thechne PCR thermocycler.

Consent and Ethics Approval

The study was approved by the ethics committee of the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital (REF ADM/TH/497/VOL1 2020). All patients were informed of the objectives of the study, and an informed consent form was presented to them before the collection of stool samples.

Statistical Analysis

The information obtained from the patient questionnaire and other relevant data from this study was entered into a computer program. Data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23, USA computer software. The data is shown in tables/figures as frequencies and proportions. The prevalence of all three methods (MZN, Antigen detection, and PCR) was obtained. The sensitivity,

specificity, and predictive values were determined following the methods of Galen and Gambino .¹¹

Results

Socio-demographic description of the study population

A total of 269 participants were recruited into the study. Out of which, 80 (29.7%) were males and 189 (70.3%) females, stratified as shown in Table 1. The population age ranged between 18 to ≥ 58 years, with the 38 to 47 age group (37.4%) accounting for most of the subjects. Based on occupation, housewives had the highest frequency (33.8%), and participants with secondary school education were the majority (54.6%).

The highest prevalence of *Cryptosporidium* infection was in males, 20(25%), compared to females, 32 (16.9%) (Table 1). The age group 18-27years had the highest prevalence of 7 (23.5%), while the lowest prevalence of 5 (11.6%) was found in the age group 48-57 years (Table 1). Patients with non/primary education recorded the highest prevalence of 19(24.1%), while patients with tertiary education recorded the lowest prevalence of 7(16.3%) (Table 1). Based on occupational status, the highest prevalence was among the patients who are farmers, 5(31.3%) (Table 1)

Table 1: Socio-demographic Characteristics of study participants

Variable	Frequency
n=269(%)	
Age (years)	
18-27	28 (10.4)
28-37	85(31.5)
38-47	101(37.4)
48-57	43(15.9)
≥58	13 (4.8)
Sex	
Male	80(29.7)
Female	189(70.3)
Level of Education	
None/ primary	79(29.4)
Secondary	147(54.6)
Tertiary	43(16.0)
Occupation	
Business	82(30.5)
Civil servant	68(25.3)
Farmer	16(5.90)
Housewife	91(33.8)
Student	12(4.65)

Prevalence of *Cryptosporidium* spp infection by Modified Ziehl-Neelsen Stain (MZN)

Recognition of oocysts of *Cryptosporidium* spp. Morphological microscopy after MZN staining is the conventional method of diagnosis of cryptosporidiosis. (Fig 1) Out of the 269 stool samples analysed, 36(13.4)

stool samples were positive for oocysts of *Cryptosporidium* spp. by microscopy. (Table 2)

Table 2: Prevalence based on sociodemographic characteristics and diagnostic technique

	Number tested (%)	MZN (+) Positive	ELISA (+) Positive	PCR (+) Positive
Gender				
Male	80 (29.7)	9	17	20
Female	189 (70.3)	27	29	32
Age				
18-27	28(10.4)	6	5	7
28-37	85(31.5)	11	16	20
38-47	101(37.4)	13	18	18
48-57	43(15.9)	6	6	5
≥58	13(4.8)	0	1	2
Occupation				
Business	82(30.5)	10	13	12
Civil servant	68(25.3)	10	12	13
Farmer	16(5.9)	1	5	5
Housewife	91(33.8)	13	14	20
Student	12(4.7)	2	2	2
Level of education				
None/Primary	79(29.4)	11	13	19
Secondary	147(54.6)	21	26	27
Tertiary	43(16.0)	4	6	7

Prevalence of *Cryptosporidium* spp infection by ELISA
 The ELISA technique showed a prevalence of 17.1%, thus yielding a higher prevalence when compared to MZN. Forty-two (42) participants were positive for ELISA antigen detection in the stool. (Table 2) Phenotypically showing a yellowish discoloration of the titer plates (Fig. 2)

Fig 1: *Cryptosporidium* oocysts stained pinkish red (examined at 100x) were observed as the thick-walled spherical structure of approximately 2-8µm in diameter

Fig 2: ELISA Plate shows yellowish wells depicting positive samples and a colorless well representing a negative sample.

3.4 Prevalence of *Cryptosporidium* spp infection by Nested PCR

Fifty-six (56) out of the 269 samples used for molecular studies were amplified (Table 2). The PCR SSU-rRNA genes produced bands with a molecular size of 1,300bp (Fig. 3). The secondary PCR products of the 18S rRNA gene yielded bands that coincided with the expected 830bp diagnostic of cryptosporidium species (Fig. 4).

Fig 3: PCR amplification products SSU rRNA gene using 1500kbp Lane 1-13; Lane 13; 1.5kbp molecular marker. Lane 12 Negative control for *Cryptosporidium spp*, Lane 1-7 clinical samples positive for *Cryptosporidium spp*, Lane 8-11 clinical samples negative for *Cryptosporidium spp*.

Fig 4: PCR gel electrophoresis showing the inner primer Cry18NA product. Using a 500bp molecular marker, 2-20 positive samples between 826 – 837 bp.

Out of the 269 patients who participated in the study, 36 (13.4%) were positive using the modified ZN staining method. MZN stain recorded a sensitivity and specificity of 30.8% and 90.8%, respectively, using PCR as a gold standard. The study found a positive predictive value of 44.4% and a negative predictive value of 84.5%. (Table 3)

Table 3: Sensitivity, Specificity, Positive predictive value, and Negative predictive value of the different test techniques for *Cryptosporidium spp* in Maiduguri

TEST METHOD	PCR +	PCR -	SENSITIVITY (%)	SPECIFICITY (%)	PPV (%)	NPV (%)
MZN POSITIVE	16	20	30.8	90.8	44.4	84.5
MZN NEGATIVE	36	197				
ELISA POSITIVE	42	4	80.8	98.2	91.3	95.5
ELISA NEGATIVE	10	213				

Discussion

The Ziehl-Neelsen conventional technique is laborious, with relatively low sensitivity and specificity when performed by inexperienced staff.¹² However, it detects only the life parasites, which could be the reason for the test's low sensitivity. This finding is similar to what was found by Aghamolaie *et al.*¹³ and contrary to what was found by Gabr *et al.*¹⁴ This variation could be because of the difference in sample size among the studies, with this study having a larger sample size. The MZN technique is laborious and less sensitive, and thus prone to error.¹⁵ The oocyst is tiny, measuring 4-6 µm, and can easily be confused with oocysts, yeast cells, and *Cyclospora spp.*¹⁶ Interestingly, this method will not differentiate between *Cryptosporidium* species because they take up red to pink colours like other faecal components. However, MZN is cheap and affordable; hence, resource-poor countries still rely on this technique.¹⁷ ELISA (antigen detection) and

PCR are more sensitive and specific; however, they are expensive and may not distinguish active from inactive infection as done by MZN.¹⁸

Another method employed in diagnosing cryptosporidiosis in this study was an antigen detection method, ELISA, which can detect the oocyst antigen for *Cryptosporidium species*. Forty-six participants were positive for cryptosporidiosis using ELISA, detecting an additional ten positives that were initially negative by MZN. A sensitivity of 80.8% and a specificity of 98.2% were obtained using PCR as the gold standard, with a positive predictive value of 91.3% and a negative predictive value of 95.5%. This is in concordance with what was found in comparative diagnostic techniques for *Cryptosporidium*¹⁹ Variations in sensitivities and specificities are understandable because the ELISA detects antigens of the pathogen, which may have been from an active infection. Likewise, the PCR technique

picks up genomes of both infective and non-infective *Cryptosporidium* oocysts, thus significantly increasing the sensitivity of both diagnostic methods. Conversely, specificity is higher with the ZN technique as mature active oocysts are mainly detected. Furthermore, the variation in the results with different test subjects may have been influenced by their previous exposure to the pathogen.²⁰

The findings in this study are similar to the conclusions of a comparative study done in Nsukka^{18,20} and contrary to the result of a similar study done in Iran²¹, which recorded a higher sensitivity for both MZN and ELISA and lower specificity; however, PCR was not used as the gold standard. PCR, a molecular detection method, gives a better advantage in grading other diagnostic techniques if used as the gold standard. In a study done in India, they found that microscopy should remain the preferred method of diagnosis for *Cryptosporidium*, having a good sensitivity and specificity,²² although this study used more robust techniques. This conclusion by the Indian study may be connected to the fact that MZN is a cheaper, more reliable, accessible, and easier technique when compared to ELISA or PCR. It is also worth mentioning that nested PCR is highly sensitive and specific for the molecular diagnosis of cryptosporidiosis because it is more successful in amplifying long DNA products than conventional PCR.²³ These were the reasons why PCR was used as a gold standard in this study.

Conclusion

The MZN staining technique was less sensitive for detecting *Cryptosporidium* in the study population; however, it has the advantage of being the only technique that indicates active infection, unlike ELISA and PCR.

Recommendation: We advocate the use of higher diagnostic and identification methods for cryptosporidiosis, like ELISA and PCR.

Declarations

Ethical approval and consent: The work is approved by the Ethical Research Committee of University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital (REF ADM/TH/497/VOL1 2020), and all participants gave informed consent before recruitment.

Consent for publication: Not applicable

Availability of data and material: The datasets are available on request from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Conflict of interest: The authors declare no competing interests

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Authors' Contribution: MUK, YMY, GBG, and KBA contributed to writing the concept notes and formulating the study design. JA and ASB, MY, MUK, and ZBS worked on data collection, data analysis and interpretation, laboratory analysis and interpretation. BBG, ABS, MD, ZG, and all the authors contributed significantly during the manuscript drafting, revision, and accept responsibility for the integrity of the data and accuracy of analyses.

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References

- Mulunda NR, Hayashida K, Yamagishi J, Sianongo S, Munsaka G, Sugimoto C, *et al.* Molecular characterisation of *Cryptosporidium* spp. From patients with diarrhoea in Lusaka, Zambia. *Parasite*. 2020;27.
- Omoruyi BE, Nwodo UU, Udem CS, Okonkwo FO. Comparative diagnostic techniques for cryptosporidium infection. *Molecules*. 2014;19(2):2674–83.
- Oyegue-Liabagui SL, Ndjangangoye NK, Kouna LC, Lekolo GM, Mounioko F, Kwedi Nolna S, *et al.* Molecular prevalence of intestinal parasite infections in children with diarrhoea in Franceville, Southeast of Gabon. *BMC Infect Dis*. 2020;20(1):350.
- Hailu AW, Degarege A, Adamu H, Costa D, Villier V, Mouhajir A, *et al.* Molecular characterisation of *Cryptosporidium* spp. From humans in Ethiopia. *PLoS One* [Internet]. 2021;16(6 June 2021):1–12. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0253186>
- Checkley W, White AC, Jaganath D, Arrowood MJ, Chalmers RM, Chen XM, *et al.* A review of the global burden, novel diagnostics, therapeutics, and vaccine targets for cryptosporidium. *Lancet Infect Dis*. 2015;15(1):85–94.
- Olopade B., Ogunniyi T., Oyekunle A., Odetoyin B., Adegoke A. Cryptosporidiosis: Prevalence, risk factors, and diagnosis in adult HIV-infected patients at Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospitals Complex (OAUTHC), Ile-Ife, Osun State, Nigeria. *Int J Med Biomed Res*. 2017;6(1):18–29.
- Bamaiyi PH, Redhuan NEM. Prevalence and risk factors for cryptosporidiosis: A global, emerging, neglected zoonosis. *Asian Biomed*. 2016;10(4):309–25.
- Squire SA, Ryan U. Cryptosporidium and Giardia in Africa: current and future challenges. *Parasites and Vectors*. 2017;10(1):1–32.
- Okojokuw Ocheme Julius, Helen Inabo, Yakubu Samuel, Okubanjo Oluseyi, Kolawale Tayo *et al.* Molecular characterisation of *Cryptosporidium* species among patients presenting with diarrhoea in some parts of Kaduna State, Nigeria. *American Journal of Research Communication*, 2016; 4 (3); 87–106.
- Manouana GP, Lorenz E, Mbong Ngwese M, Nguema Moure PA, Maiga Ascofare *et al.* Performance of a rapid diagnostic test for the detection of *Cryptosporidium* spp in African children admitted to hospital with diarrhea. *PLOS Negl. Trop. Dis* 2020 14(7)
- Semmani M, Costa D, Achour N, Cherchar M, Ziane H, Mouhajir A, *et al.* Occurrence and Molecular Characterization of *Cryptosporidium* Infection in HIV/Aids Patients in Algeria. *Viruses*. 2023;15(2).

13. S.A Nassar, A.F Kolade, A.S Oluremi, M.A Adeleye. Comparison of the two diagnostic methods used for the detection of *Cryptosporidium* infection among HIV patients in Osogbo, Nigeria. *Journal of Advances in Medicine and Medical Research* 2018;27(4):1-7
14. Aghamolaie S, Rostami A, Fallahi Sh, Tahvildar Biderouni F, Haghghi A, Salehi N. Evaluation of modified Ziehl-Neelsen, direct fluorescent-antibody and PCR assay for detection of *Cryptosporidium spp.* in children's foecal specimens. *J Parasit Dis.* 2016 Sep [cited 2020 Apr 17];40(3):958-63.
15. Gabr NS, Abdellatif MZM, Abd El-Hafeez EH. Comparison between ELISA and Various Staining Techniques in Laboratory Diagnosis of Cryptosporidiosis. *JESP.* 2014;44(2):509-16.
16. C. Chique, P.D. Hynds, L.Andrade, L Burke, D Morris, M.P. Ryan, J. O'Dwyer. *Cryptosporidium spp* in groundwater supplies intended for human consumption - A descriptive review of global prevalence, risk factors and knowledge gaps. *Water Research* 2020;176:115726.
17. Saha R, Saxena B, Jamir ST, Shekhar S. Prevalence of Cryptosporidiosis in symptomatic immunocompetent children and comparative evaluation of its diagnosis by Ziehl-Neelsen staining and antigen detection technique. *Trop Parasitol* 2019;9:18-22.
18. Choy RKM, Huston CD. Cryptosporidiosis should be designated as a tropical disease by the US Food and Drug Administration. *PLoS Neglected Trop Dis* 2020;14(7): e0008252.
19. Blatu Gebre, Tsegaye Alemayehu, Mekonin Girma, Freshwork Ayalew, Birkneh Tilahun Tadesse *et al.* Cryptosporidiosis and Other intestinal parasitic infections and concomitant threats among HIV-infected children in South Ethiopia receiving First-line antiretroviral therapy. *HIV AIDS Research and Palliative Care* 2019;11. 299-306.
20. Manouana GP, Lorenz E, Mbonh Ngwese M, Nguema Moure PA, Maige Ascofare O, Akenten CW *et al.* Performance of rapid diagnostic test for the detection of *Cryptosporidium spp* in African children admitted to hospital with diarrhoea *PLoS Negl Trop Dis* 2020;14(7) e000844.
21. Farid Tahvildar-Biderouni, Nima Salehi. Detection of *Cryptosporidium* infection by modified Ziehl-Neelsen and PCR methods in children with diarrheal samples in paediatric hospitals in Tehran, Gastroenterology and Hepatology From Bed to Bench.©2014 *RIGLD, Research Institute for Gastroenterology and Liver Diseases* 2014;7(2):125-130.
22. Saha R, Saxena R, Saxena B, Jamir ST, Shekhar S. Prevalence of cryptosporidiosis in symptomatic immunocompetent children and a comparative evaluation of its diagnosis by Ziehl-Neelsen staining and antigen detection techniques. *Trop Parasitol* 2019;9:18-22.
23. Iman Abdelsalam, Rania Mohammed Sarhan, Marmar Ahmed Hanafy. The impact of different copro-preservation conditions on molecular detection of *Cryptosporidium* species. *Iran J Parasitol* 2017;12(2) 274-283.